

DATA SECURITY AND INTEGRITY IN CLOUD COMPUTING ENVIRONMENT: AN APPROACH FOR E-BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

Today's technical and business landscape presents formidable and evolving challenges to personal data privacy. Cloud Computing is a style of computing that provides convenient on-demand network access to a shared pool of configurable computing resources that can be rapidly deployed with great efficiency and minimal management overhead. Personal data stored in the Cloud could be used or misused by a miscreants, competitors, or persons desirous of fraudulent motives. These data are cached, copied, and archived by Cloud Service Providers (CSPs), often without users' authorization and control. In practical, self-destructing data systems secure sensitive data from disclosure in our highly mobile, social-networked, cloud-computing world. This study validates a self-destructive data security system using files of different formats and a secure metadata server to make an improvement on the existing models. All data and their copies become unreadable when an attempt to copy the file from the secure server is made and it creates a fault log to notify the administrator on an attack. This research adopted the object-oriented analysis and design methodology (OOADM) and was implemented using Php programming language and MYSQL for relational database (RDB). The model has been developed, tested and was able to deny unauthorized users access to the files stored on the cloud storage and was able to notify the admin through electronic mailing system of any threat in the system. The efficiency of the proposed model was evaluated using performance metrics and showed that the proposed model is robust and more efficient than other existing related models

INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing took the world by storm, now recognized as one, if not the most popular technology in the Information Technology (IT) Industries. Day by Day, a wide range of companies and businesses are becoming more habituated to using many applications of cloud computing because of its pay as-you-use nature, where clients need not to worry about purchasing assets such as hardware, programs, framework etc., as cost is reduced drastically when compared to the traditional model of computing and the ease at which IT infrastructure solution offered (Ara et al., 2020; Srinivasan et al., 2022). Cloud computing can be termed as providing information technology resources when demanded through the internet. The whole concept of its operation is in the notion that the work done (data and software) on the client side can be transferred to an unseen cluster of resources on the internet (Ajoudanian & Ahmadi, 2022). Cloud computing being a virtual environment has its special security threats and these threats are by far different from the threats in physical systems. This has led to companies and businesses refusing to fully adopt moving to cloud computing environment. In this study, these security concerns will be properly examined and improved upon to be able to give those with doubt the trust to fully embrace cloud computing.

Data Security is the protection of data from an unauthorized user, theft or corruption and thereby providing a high security standard to avoid modification and interception of sensitive data in transmission (Poza, 2021). Securing sensitive data has raised eyebrow in recent time due to massive increase in transfer, research, and transaction over the internet (cloud environment). In order to improve on data transmission over the internet securely, different techniques has been revised with sophisticated approaches such as encryption terminologies in cloud (Singh, 2022)

Data integrity is the maintenance of and the assurance of data accuracy and consistency over its entire life-cycle” (Ara et. al.2020). Data integrity also make sure that data is kept safe from third party force and the data is always accurate and reliable irrespective of the period it has been stored or how regularly the data is being accessed. Every business and organization invest heavily to keep their confidential data from unauthorized modification thereby enforcing different policies to achieve this.

Electronic Business used interchangeably with e-business is define as the overall term that envelops all form that uses of Digital information and communication technology to help and streamline business measures (Pratt and Cole, 2021). With the 24 hour/7 days availability of the internet, and the global exposure and related legal risks associated with the absence of territorial boundaries as well as business hour limitations provide a strong possibility that customers from around the world will visit sites. Today’s technical and legal landscape presents formidable challenges to personal data privacy. First, our increasing reliance on Web services causes personal data to be cached, copied, and archived by third parties, often without our knowledge or control. Second, the disclosure of private data has become common place due to carelessness, theft, or legal actions. Our research seeks to protect the privacy of past, archived data such as copies of emails maintained by an email provider against accidental, malicious, and legal attacks. Specifically, we wish to ensure that all copies of certain data become unreadable after a user-specified time, without

any specific action on the part of a user, and even if an attacker obtains both a cached copy of that data and the user's cryptographic keys and passwords. (Geambasu et al., 2024). This study presents Vanish, a system that meets this challenge through a novel integration of cryptographic techniques with global-scale, P2P, distributed hash tables (DHTs). We implemented a proof-of-concept Vanish prototype to use both the million-plus-node Vuze Bit-Torrent DHT and the restricted-membership Open DHT. We evaluate experimentally and analytically the functionality, security, and performance properties of Vanish, demonstrating that it is practical to use and meets the privacy-preserving goals described. We also describe two applications those we prototyped on Vanish: a Firefox plug in for Gmail and other Websites and a Vanishing File application.

Overview of Data Security and Integrity

Data protection attempts to ensure the security of computer-processed data from unauthorized access, from destructive user actions, and from computer failure. With increasing use of computer-based information systems, there has been increasing concern for the protection of computer-processed data. Data protection is closely allied with other functional areas. The design of data entry, data display, sequence control, user guidance, and data transmission functions can potentially affect the security of the data being processed. In many applications, however, questions of data protection require explicit consideration. (Rajendra,2024). Data protection must deal with two general problems. First, data must be protected from unauthorized access and tampering. This is the problem of data security. Second, data must be protected from errors by authorized system users, in effect to protect users from their own mistakes. This is the problem of error prevention. Design techniques to achieve data security and to prevent user errors are necessarily different, but for both purposes the designer must resolve a fundamental dilemma. How can the user interface be designed to make correct, legitimate transactions easy to accomplish, while making mistaken or unauthorized transactions difficult? In each system application, a balance must be struck between these fundamentally conflicting design objectives. Concern for data security will take different forms in different system applications. Individual users may be concerned with personal privacy and wish to limit access to private data files. Corporate organizations may seek to protect data related to proprietary interests. Military agencies may be responsible for safeguarding data critical to national security. (Dharmik, 2024) The mechanisms for achieving security will vary accordingly. Special passwords might be required to access private files. Special log-on procedures might be required to assure positive identification of authorized users, with records kept of file access and data changes. Special confirmation codes might be required to validate critical commands.

At the extreme, measures instituted to protect data security may be so stringent that they handicap normal system operations. Imagine a system in which security measures are designed so that every command must be accompanied by a continuously changing validation code which a user has to remember. Imagine further that when the user makes a code error, which can easily happen under stress, the command sequence is interrupted to re-initiate a user identification procedure. In such a system, there seems little doubt that security measures will reduce operational effectiveness. In

recent years, computer security measures have concentrated increasingly on automatic means for data protection, implemented by physical protection of computing equipment and by tamper-proof software. Automation of security makes good sense. If data security can be assured by such means, there will be less needed to rely on fallible human procedures. And, of course, user interface design will be that much easier (Davis, 2023).

Data Security Concept

Data security is the process that takes into consideration all the necessary measures in place to keep digital data from unauthorized users, either in the form of destruction, use, disclosure, disruption and modification. In the bid to keep data safe in all its location i.e. within an organization perimeter and the system where data is created, processed, stored, transmitted and destroyed free from threats mostly in big organization where confidential data disclosure either accidentally or deliberately can be catastrophe. Threats to these data and system may be categorized and adequate security goal be defined for each threats category (Peltier & Thomas, 2023). A collection of the aforementioned security goal which are identified as a result of threats are confidentiality, integrity, availability, privacy, authenticity and trust worthiness, on-repudiation, accountability and durability. The advent of information technology has erupted issues on privacy and security of data and information. It has thrown them into a new limelight and provides means for breaching and protecting the security of data. Countering the disclosure of confidential information, privacy transformation is the most effective technical measure to be implemented, better known as data encryption (Stallings, 2021). Data security and cryptography are intertwined, and they share a common service of protecting the integrity, availability and confidentiality of electronic data. In encryption process, data security utilizes cryptograph to shift the digital data into cipher form which prevents its usage from unauthorized individual (Cherdantseva and Hilton, 2023).

Technique for Data Security

Cryptography is one of the most important field in computer security, it is the process of transferring data and information through an open network that only the receiver with the message key will be able to get the content of the message which might be video, document, audio, and other data form. Cryptography is used implementing privacy. Cryptography scrabbles the data and others without the right key will not be able to access the actual information. Cryptography in general help ensure the following (Xu et al., 2024).

- i. Confidentiality: this is a service used to guarantee information. it is accessible only to authorized entities and is inaccessible to other.
- ii. Non-repudiation: this is a service use to confirm the involvement of an entity in a certain form of communication and prevents any party from denying the sent messages.
- iii. Integrity: this is a service that guarantees the correctness of information and data. It ensures that information remains unchanged from source to destination.
- iv. Accessibility: this service allows the use of resources only by the authorized personnel.

Methodology

The Object-Oriented Analysis and Design methodology was adopted for this research. This methodology uses a collection of interrelated objects to model a system, just like objects in the real life; each object has attributes and set of operations.

Figure 3.1: The Proposed System Architecture

Explanation of the Proposed Architecture

Metadata server (MDS): MDS is responsible for user management, server management, session management and file metadata management. The metadata server provides information about a virtual machine scheduling option through the scheduling/metadata directory entry and the maintenance-event attributed. The functionality of the metadata for a document is to collect the information like the author, file size, the data the document was created, and keywords to describe the document.

Application node: The application node is used to store the services in the metadata modules, and the self-destructive system. It consists of the mechanism used in encrypting and decrypting the data. The SeDas encryption uses the symmetric way/pattern of securing data. The key been used in uploading the file is still used to decrypt such file when in use. The encryption in the AES and DES is as follows. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is also a symmetric key block cipher. AES was published in 2001 by the National Institute of Standards and Technology. AES was introduced to replace DES as DES uses very small cipher key and the algorithm was quite slower.

AES algorithm takes 128-bit plaintext and 128-bit secret key which together forms a 128-bit block which is depicted as 4 X 4 square matrix. This 4 X 4 square matrix undergoes an initial transformation and is used to secure the data in cloud environment. This step is followed by the 10 rounds. Among which 9 round contain following stages:

- **Subbytes:** It uses S-box by which it performs byte by byte substitution of the entire block (matrix).
- **Shift Rows:** Rows of the matrix are shifted.
- **Mix Columns:** Columns are of the matrix are shuffled from right to left.
- **Add round keys:** Here, the Xor of the current block and the expanded key is performed.

Algorithm for the Proposed System:

Uploading the file using AES key algorithm for key splitting and the procedure to Upload File (data, key,)

Uploading the file using AES key algorithm for key splitting
Procedure to Upload File (data, key)

Data: data read from this file to be uploaded

Key: data read from the key

Begin//encrypt the input data with the key

 Buffer = Encrypt (data, key)

 if failed then return fail;

Create file in the data storage node and write buffer into it;

// use AES key algorithm to get key shares

// k is count of data servers in the SeDas system

 Shared keys [1....k] = AES key Split (n, k, key)

 For i from 1 to k then

 Connect to SN[i]

If successful then create object (shared keys [i],);

 Then store in server

Else

```
For j from 1 to i then
    End for
    Return fail;
End if
End for
    Return successful;
End.
```


Figure 3.2: Front and Backend diagram of the Proposed Architecture

Explanation: The front-end comprises of the user name and password for existing users and sign up for a new user. The backend /server-side of the system comprises of the working dynamic database and the process engine. The tools used in building this side of the system are PHP, WAMP/XAMPP (comprising of the local server with the MySQL Database) and SQL.

Results

Figure 4.1: User Login Screen

Figure 4.1 shows the user login screen which is the first page on the web application. An existing user only needs to supply login details to be granted access while a new user must register before login.

Figure 4.2: Data Entries Interface

Figure 4.2 shows the data entries present in the system with serial no, title and the document name.

Figure 4.3: Upload Interface

Figure 4.3 shows the upload data interface and how data gains entry into the system and is also saved in cloud for future reference.

Figure 4.4: Download Page

Figure 4.4 shows the download page where pre stored data can be downloaded from the cloud.

Performance Evaluation

In this data security system, several matrices were used in the evaluation testing such as the file size, the time for upload and download, neural network tool in Matlab, one considered the most recent tools used Method like the DES (Data Encryption Standard algorithm) and compared it with AES (Advance Encryption Algorithm) and the throughput. This section explained in detail how the performance for the upload time and download time for the proposed system is faster than other existing models. The data which is to be transmitted from sender to receiver in the network must be encrypted using the encryption algorithm in cryptography. The tables 4.1 record the performance of existing and proposed system in terms of file size (in MegaByte) and time (in seconds) for uploading file to cloud and downloading files from cloud and are represented in the histograms in figures 4.5 and 4.9 and line graphs.

Figure 4.5: A Histogram of throughput for upload

Figure 4.6: A graph of throughput for upload

While Fig 4.6 shows throughput for upload. X axis represents the throughput; Y axis represents the file size. Throughput is how much megabyte is calculated in one second. For other models, 16mb was uploaded in 40s, whereas in proposed system it takes 20s to upload a 16mb file. Compared to the already existing models, the performance of proposed system is higher. This graph clearly shows the proposed system reduces the throughput over already existing models by an average of 15.5% and up to 55% for the uploading.

Figure 4.7: Graph of Neural Network training Performance AES Algorithm

Figure 4.7 shows the performance for AES Algorithm, when subjected to the NNTOOL it shows a best validation performance 54912, 6077, while the DES shows its best validation at 1659.7703

Figure 4.8: Graph of Neural Network training Performance DES Algorithm.

This figure 4.8 and observably Fig4.7, does not indicate any major problems with the training. The validation and test curves are very similar. If the test curve had increased significantly before the validation curve increased, then it is possible that some overfitting might have occurred.

Figure 4.9: Neural network Training State for AES Algorithm

Figure 4.9 mu is the control parameter for the algorithm used to train the neural network. Choice of mu directly affects the error convergence as shown. While the gradient measures the steepness

between file encrypted against number of iterations. The graph measures proportionality between encrypted file and number of iterations. The sharp steepness in the graph shows lack of proportionate between file encrypted and the corresponding algorithm chosen can be noticed that the steepness in the graph for an AES is less than that of DES in figure 4.10 and 4.11 respectively.

Figure 4.10: Neural network Training State for DES Algorithm

Figure 4.11: Graph of Matlab Regression tool for R test AES Algorithm

Figure 4.12: Graph of Matlab Regression tool for R test DES Algorithm

Figure 4.11 and 4.12 is a regression test showing the level of the validation and test results also show R values that greater than 0.9, the AES has higher R value than DES for figure 11 and 12. The three plots represent the training, validation, and testing data. The dashed line in each plot represents the perfect result – outputs = targets. The solid line represents the best fit linear regression line between outputs and targets. The R value is an indication of the relationship between the outputs and targets. If $R = 1$, this indicates that there is an exact linear relationship between outputs and targets. If R is close to zero, then there is no linear relationship between outputs and targets.

Figure 4.13: Result of File Access with Right Permissive

Figure 4.13 shows that with right permission and authentic access granted, a user can access saved documents on the cloud environment freely without hitches.

Figure 4.14: Result of Self Destructive Encrypted Unreadable Data

Figure 4.14 shows the result emanated from the cloud computing environment using self-destructive mechanism. The result is generated when an unauthorized person get access to such data. It is an improvement of other existing systems by eradicating the use of timer. The flop in the other systems was that an unauthorized user can still steal the data with the use of timer constraints by having a screen shot or snap the file since he/she can view the file for some time before it become unreadable. The improvement made now is that an unauthorized user cannot view any encrypted file because timer has been eradicated; rather, user can view the unreadable file as displayed.

Discussion of the Results

Firstly the data which is to be transmitted from sender to receiver in the network was encrypted using the encryption algorithm in cryptography. Secondly, by using decryption technique the receiver can view the original data. In this thesis, we implemented two encrypt techniques like AES, DES algorithms and compared their performance of encrypt techniques based on the analysis of its stimulated time at the time of encryption and decryption. The result of the proposed system using the right permissive value is shown in the figure 4.13, while using a wrong permissive trying to steal or retrieved the data is very unreadable which is shown in the figure 4.14 and indicates the results from the generated from the software developed and very visible for the end-users when any registered user input the right authentication required for the data to be retrieved from the cloud environment.

Conclusion

Security risks have been analyzed with utmost attention on secure cloud data storage. Several existing encryption algorithms were for secure cloud data storage were also evaluated and then an approach for ensuring data confidentiality and integrity was proposed. The approach is a

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combination of two proven techniques: Advanced Encryption Standard and DES Algorithm are used to achieve more robust and secured data storage, even if the data is stolen, it will become unreadable to the intruder. For our contribution to knowledge Firstly, metadata server was implemented to keep hold of the information stored in the SeDas storage and improve the quality of accessing those data. Secondly, self-destructive system was implemented to destroy files on attack on the system without user intervention.

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